

Appendix 1: Signatories of the 2030 Declaration on Scientific Plant and Fungal Collecting

Version 3

23 January 2025: 977 signatories across 90 countries

This appendix accompanies the Antonelli et al. (2024) paper entitled ‘The 2030 Declaration on Scientific Plant and Fungal Collecting’ (accepted for publication in *Plants, People, Planet*).

An open call was posted on the website of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew in March 2024 (<https://kew.org/2030-declaration>) inviting people to show their support for the 2030 Declaration and its five commitments. Visitors to the page were invited to read the full draft of the Declaration and fill in a form to become a signatory. Respondents could opt to become individual or organisational signatories, or both. At the time of publication of the Declaration manuscript, 851 signatories across 85 countries worldwide had signed up to show their support (59 co-authors, 679 other individuals and 113 organisations). By 31 December 2024, this had risen to 977 signatories across 90 countries (59 co-authors, 790 other individuals and 128 organisations; see lists of signatories below). Figures S1 to S3 display summary data for the individual signatories relating to their primary taxonomic group of interest, fields of expertise and primary sphere of work.

Figure S1: Primary taxonomic group of interest of individual signatories (780 respondents)

Figure S2: Fields of expertise of individual signatories (690 respondents, multiple answers permitted)

Figure S3: Primary sphere of work of individual signatories (680 respondents)

Signatories of the 2030 Declaration on Scientific Plant and Fungal Collecting (977)

All lists are alphabetical by first name.

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Conservatoire et Jardin Botanique de Genève, Switzerland
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